

Wearable Body Temperature Sensing with Autonomous Self-regulated Joule Heating and Passive Cooling for Healthcare Applications

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Conventional hardware for wearables

- Maintaining precise thermal management.

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Positive temperature coefficient (PTC) effect

- Conductive polymer composites (CPCs)
- Matrix expands, disrupting the conductive network
- Restoring conductive network when polymer contracts
- Dynamic self-regulation

Food-inspired thermal responsive material

Bio-based

Why nano?

GNPs

CNTs

AgNWs

Why 2D? – High aspect ratio

Thermal expansion

- ~~Store easily~~ **Store easily** separate poly(styrene-styrene (SEBS)
- ~~flexibility and ductility~~ **flexibility and ductility** active pathways
- ~~Maintain high thermal conductivity~~ **Maintain high thermal conductivity** PTC effect

Hongxu Guo et al. Adv. Funct. Mater. 2025, 35, 2417961.

SEBS: *CC(C1=CC=CC=C1)CC(C)CC(C)CC(C1=CC=CC=C1)*

Lauric acid: CCCCCCCCCCCC(=O)O

GNPs: Graphene Nanoplatelets

Hot stage optical microscopy

Multifunctional nanocomposite

- Thermal expansion mismatch and dilution of the conductive network
- Significant expansion during heating
- GNP migration and network disruption
- Reversible phase change process

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PTC Effect Optimisation

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Ultra-sensitive wearable temperature monitoring

Temperature coefficient of resistance:

$$TCR = \frac{(R_2 - R_1)}{R_1(T_2 - T_1)} \times 100\%$$

Key Features:

- Ultra high TCR !
- Low-grade fever detection
- Fast and reliable response time

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Practical applications

Wearable healthcare devices

Heating

Temperature sensing and regulation

Breathing

Cooling

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Key message

Fatty acid

Temperature sensing

Overcurrent protection¹

De-icing²

Positive temperature coefficient (PTC)
Nanocomposite